

Reproducing Cross-lingual Document Retrieval using Regularized Wasserstein Distance

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ABSTRACT

Many research papers published often either don't include code which was used to obtain the presented results or share code that does not provide a good base to reproduce the findings. Very often the source code provided doesn't match the requirements of reproducibility, in order to future proof themselves. Thus, in this project we have chosen *Cross-Lingual Document Retrieval Using Regularised Wasserstein Distance*[1] as our example paper to test if the project is reproducible. This paper presents the strategies taken and explains the steps of testing the results of the 4 year old original research paper as well as compares the findings of the reproduced results. As with any coding project, specifying the programming language, OS and dependencies with their version can be crucial and time saving for anyone who wants to reproduce the results.

KEYWORDS

wasserstein distance, cross-lingual document retrieval, python

STRATEGIES

As the code of the research paper was provided via a repository on the software development hosting platform GitHub, the first step was to clone the source files and run them according to the attached instruction on local machines. In this step already many reproducing efforts usually fail because of insufficient instruction from the developers side or the code containing errors. The same was the case during the execution of this project. The first problem was that many parts of the code were not running correctly, returning many error messages. Some of them warned about errors in the syntax, as well as semantic problems with matrix calculations. After a long investigation into the failures it turned out that the code was optimised on a older version of Python, which does not work with the current versions. Any mention of the correct Python version was lacking in the instructions.

1 DOCUMENTATION

Due to a lack of proper documentation in the paper and on Github[2], it became quite challenging to reproduce the whole project properly. Without the appropriate domain knowledge it is very difficult to reproduce the outcome that is true to the original paper. In the documentation itself there is no hint to which Python version was used, nor is there any information about which further packages should be installed to run the code. Another issue was that in the code itself there were some minor errors. For example, the print function was adapted to an older python version, which led in the newer

versions to numerous syntax errors. For better reproducibility we created a Github repository[3] with all changes to get the initial project running as well as a `.yml` file with all necessary parameters in order to be able to recreate the results.

2 LANGUAGE PACKAGES

The aim of this experiment was to reproduce and test the methods on more than two languages. Yet due to the lack of documentation and information about the access to crucial packages or appropriate reprocessing methods made this endeavour impossible. Despite finding text files in the sub-folder of the project called `wiki_data`, which seemed to be similar to the ones from the website referenced in the paper, the file sizes differed significantly. The file with different languages referenced in the paper had a size of 3 gigabytes, while the ones used in the paper had size of 10 megabytes. This indicated that heavy pre-processing steps are necessary in order to apply this code on.

3 OPERATING SYSTEM AND PROCESSOR

Another major issue was that neither the paper nor the code instructions specified which operating system should be used in order to be able to run the files. As there was no information about it the assumption was that the code is working cross platform. This however was not the case. After trying to run the source files on the to us available operating systems macOS and Ubuntu, both running on the latest versions, it became quickly evident that the code is not optimized on multiple platforms. MacOS didn't support many of the packages needed to reproduce the results. Even switching to the intended Python 2.7 version was not possible because this version did not support Apple's ARM processor M1.

The original code was also not compatible with Ubuntu 21.10, however with some modifications to the script it was possible to run.

4 PYTHON

As already mentioned, the version differences in Python were a major issue when running the code. Nothing in the research paper or script instructions indicated on the intended version of Python which posed a special challenge. The same issue were the used libraries, which had different versions and only specific ones were appropriate to run with the given code. In order to tackle this obstacle, a Python virtual environment with `conda`[4] was created. The entire virtual environment can be found in the Github repository provided by this paper.

5 PERFORMANCE (VM LINUX)

After fixing the errors and setting everything up, some test runs were made with the slightly modified code. Since Ubuntu was the only operating system it worked on, performance and resources were limited. With the virtual machine in use, consisting of 6 cores and 16 gigabytes of random-access memory (RAM), the run-time was about 3 hours and 15 minutes. This is a significant increase compared to the graphic provided on Github[2], with it implying a run-time of less than 400 seconds for Entro_Wass and less than 200 seconds for regular Wasserstein with a 6-core processor.

6 RESULTS

The following table will compare the results from the original paper with the ones we could reproduce.

	Original		Reproduced	
	En → Fr	Fr → En	En → Fr	Fr → En
$Wass_{tf}^*$.744	.748	.740	.749
$Wass_{idf}^*$.778	.784	.779	.789
$Entro_Wass_{tf}^*$.753	.786	.752	.787
$Entro_Wass_{idf}^*$.799	.820	.795	.825

Table 1: Tabular comparison of original with reproduced values

Figure 1: Comparison between original and reproduced values for $Wass_{tf}^*$

Figure 2: Comparison between original and reproduced values for $Wass_{idf}^*$

Figure 3: Comparison between original and reproduced values for $Entro_Wass_{tf}^*$

Figure 4: Comparison between original and reproduced values for $Entro_Wass_{idf}^*$

We could reproduce almost the exact same values from the paper. The biggest error is 0.005/0.5%. The reason for this could be that Ubuntu was used, while the research paper used a different OS. However this is impossible to verify because of the lack of information about it.

7 HOW TO USE

We recommend using native Linux OS for a seamless start, otherwise use windows with x86 architecture to create a Linux VM environment. Our VM used Ubuntu version 21.10. Avoid macOS especially the one with ARM architecture. After setting your VM install Conda[5] and load our Conda environment file `.yml`. If you want to clone the repo from the source be aware that their source code has some minor issues. Instead our provided repository can be used. Follow the instructions stated in the `README` file in our Github repository.

8 CONCLUSION

After going through the original paper, making a proper documentation for each file you include is crucial. Steps for reproduction are essential, like how certain files can be created or recreated, what kind of preprocessing has been done and which packages to use.

Also any involved code should contain enough details about which OS, which hardware or CPU architecture, which programming language, which versions and which exact dependencies were used. These simple steps can save a lot of time and effort getting the needed information, especially if the code is working on different version and producing errors that can lead the user to think something is wrong with code not a software or hardware version.

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